

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B193
Date: 27 Apr 2006
Take Off 10:00:18
Landing: 15:17:27
Flight Time 5h17m19

Campaign: VISURB
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: South coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
6	Cloud physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
7	Wet Neph / PSAP	Simon Osborne	Met Office
8	Wet Neph / PSAP Training	Andy Wilson	Met Office
9	Core Chem / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
10	AMS	Gerard Capes	Manchester University
11	IR Camera	Joss Kent	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
13	MARSS / ARIES	James Bowles	Met Office
14			
15			
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Flight Track:

B193 Track 27-APR-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b193
 Date: 27 Apr 2006
 Project: VISURB
 Location: South coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
093410		starting position	0.00 kft	128	52'04.36N 0'37.48W
100018		T/O	0.00 kft	212	cranfield
101222			11.0 kft	047	qnh 1024
101418	102645	Profile 1	11.0 - 0.25 kft	048	qnh 1023 waypt 87 @ 1000ft
101432		Video	10.8 kft	048	FFC 1 UFC1
102645	102753	Profile 2	-.25 - 0.5 kft	114	
102833	114704	Run 1	0.14 - 0.19 kft	120	500ft @ waypoint 45
103325			0.21 kft	138	way point 40
104852		event	0.20 kft	193	way point 41
110201		event	0.18 kft	205	way point 42
110457			0.23 kft	232	1025 qhh
111515		event	0.21 kft	267	way point 43
113109		event	0.19 kft	256	way point 44
114355		Video	0.15 kft	223	UFC2 FFC2
114704	115531	Profile 3	0.19 - 8.0 kft	271	waypoint45 1000ft/min 500ft to FL80 /min
115531	120056	Profile 4.1	8.0 - 4.0 kft	272	
120450	120832	Profile 4.2	4.0 - 0.63 kft	092	interrupt 4000'
120833	123245	Run 2	0.62 - 0.64 kft	087	
121845					waypoint 45
120945		zero	0.64 kft	088	jw and nez
122624		Ship 1	0.66 kft	029	
123323		Ship 2	0.72 kft	048	
123418		Ship 3	0.69 kft	051	
123457		Ship 4	0.72 kft	070	
123714		Ship 5	0.63 kft	236	
123754		Ship 6	0.67 kft	245	
123848		Ship 7	0.69 kft	228	
124204		Ship 8	0.66 kft	007	
124313		Ship 9	0.64 kft	093	
124402		Ship 10	0.61 kft	047	
124459	132947	Run 3	0.63 - 0.74 kft	102	
124724		pressure	0.66 kft	090	qnh 1026
130013		event	0.68 kft	049	waypoint 43
131214		Ship 11	0.73 kft	061	
131256		Ship 12	0.71 kft	064	
131308		Ship 13	0.73 kft	059	
131410		Ship 14	0.70 kft	066	
131435		event	0.79 kft	036	waypoint 42
131528		Ship 15	0.69 kft	002	
131542		Ship 16	0.73 kft	002	
131626		Ship 17	0.68 kft	019	
131705		Ship 18	0.68 kft	009	
132249		Ship 19	0.76 kft	009	
132358		Ship 20	0.68 kft	024	
132418		Ship 21	0.67 kft	022	
132927		Ship 22	0.65 kft	004	
133227		Ship 23	0.62 kft	224	
133256		Ship 24	0.67 kft	219	
133314		Ship 25	0.69 kft	229	
133357	133433	Profile 5	0.66 - 1.1 kft	186	to 1500'
133433	140525	Run 4	1.1 - 1.2 kft	184	
133820		Ship 26	1.2 kft	170	
133925		Ship 27	1.2 kft	183	
134647		Ship 28	1.1 kft	211	waypoint 42
135941		Ship 29	1.1 kft	267	waypoint 43
140714	140933	Profile 6.1	1.2 - -.08 kft	081	
140934	141438	Profile 6.2	-.08 - 4.6 kft	076	saw tooths
141438	142004	Profile 6.3	4.6 - -.06 kft	054	250' to 5000ft

142004	142503	Profile 6.4	-.06 - 4.3 kft	060
142503	143159	Profile 6.5	4.3 - -.06 kft	056
142642		turn	3.5 kft	021 waypoint 42
143159	143231	Profile 6.6	-.06 - 0.16 kft	019
143232	144143	Run 5	0.16 - 0.19 kft	018 @ 500'
144224	144826	Profile 7	0.18 - 6.5 kft	313
145110		ASP	6.5 kft	305 closed
144826	145331	Run 6	6.5 kft	304
145340	145537	Profile 8	6.5 - 8.5 kft	305
145537	150217	Run 7	8.5 kft	269
150217	150750	Profile 9	8.2 - 3.2 kft	280
150750	150939	Profile 10	3.4 - 4.2 kft	234
150939	151351	Run 8	4.2 - 4.0 kft	244
151727		Land	0.00 kft	029
152320		complete stop	0.01 kft	309
152338		final position	0.01 kft	309 52'04.36N 0'37.50W

B193 Track 27-APR-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

VISURB-UK: Assessment of aerosol properties related to urban visibility

Flight No: B193

Date: 27th April 2006

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling of aerosol properties and their effect on radiation.

Location:

Over ocean areas downwind of major pollution sources. Areas to from off the coast of the Fens (point 87) to the south coast (point 46).

Points:

#87: 53N, 1E.

#40: 5250N, 1.5E.

#41: 5153N, 1.47E.

#42: 5105N, 1.3E.

#43: 5040N, 1.0W.

#44: 5040N, 1.00W.

#45: 5001N, 2.0W.

#46: 5001N, 3.25W.

Weather:

High loadings of atmospheric aerosols. Cloudless skies preferred, but not essential.

Special requirements:

Check the mesoscale model forecast for the position of aerosol plumes before flying.

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometer/Wet-nephelometer

AMS

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS

SHIMS

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 11:00L.
2. Transit and then perform a profile descent at 1000ft/min to 50ft at point #87 [30mins].
3. Perform SLR at altitude to be determined by the mission scientist (likely 1000ft -> 4000ft from:
4. #87 -> #40 [10mins, T=40mins].
5. #40 -> #41 [20mins, T=60mins].
6. #41 -> #42 [20mins, T=80mins].
7. #42 -> #43 [10mins, T=90mins].
8. #43 -> #44 [20mins, T=110mins].
9. #44 -> #45 [20mins, T=130mins].

10. #45 -> #46 [15mins, T=145mins].
11. On reaching #45, an area for intensive operations will be determined by the mission scientist in the region #42 -> #45. This operating region will be concentrated on for ~90minutes and will consist of SLRs at a range of altitudes and a range of distances from the south coast to end up at #42 [105mins, T=250mins].
12. Perform a SLR from #42 -> #41 [20mins, T=270mins].
13. Transit from point #41 towards Cranfield [20mins, 290mins].
14. Perform a paperclip manoeuvre into landing [10mins, T=300mins].

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B193

Date: 27 April 2006

Sortie Objectives: VISURB/NEON flight. To investigate the spatial distribution, and in-situ properties of urban aerosols around the UK for comparison with the aerosol model within the UK Mesoscale Model. Additional NEON work investigating the IR images of ships and the Canfield runway.

Operating area: Off the coast of south east/south England.

Weather: Slack northerly/north-westerly flow across the UK advecting pollution from the UK across the channel. Highest pollution levels close to Dover – probably from the London conurbation. Variable amounts of cloud present throughout the flight and therefore unlikely to be useful in terms of radiation validation. Sea state 1-2 for the majority of the flight.

Flight Patterns: Subsequent to take-off the aircraft manoeuvred to a position off the coast of N. Norfolk and performed a profile descent to 250ft (point #87). The aircraft then proceeded along a clockwise track around the UK at 500ft altitude all the way round to off the coast of south Devon (marked as R1). Off the coast of East Anglia, relatively clean conditions predominated (nephelometer green scattering of around $40 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$) but peaked around the Dover area at $150 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$ before decreasing to $60 \times 10^{-6} \text{m}^{-1}$ close to Dorset (point #45). A number of ships were noted on this SLR, particularly moored off Felixstowe, and Southampton, as well as significant moving ship traffic around the Dover area. Between Point #45 and point #46 a profile ascent to 8000ft was performed to map the vertical profile of the aerosols, which showed a diffuse top of aerosol at around 5000ft. A reciprocal turn was performed and a profile descent was then performed to 1000ft and a reciprocal anti-clockwise SLR at 1000ft was performed back around the UK. This run was broken off to the south of the Isle of Wight to investigate the IR signal of moored ships using the IRCamera. Three passes were performed across the fleet of moored ships at 1000ft ASL – a total of ten ships were targeted. Subsequently a new run was commenced (should be marked R3 on Aircraft Scientist log at 12:44). Some drizzle and interesting structure on the PCASP structure/neph scattering was noted around these drizzle events. A few ships of opportunity were targeted for IRC work until we reached point #41 close to Felixstowe. Some more ship chasing was then performed (11 targets). A similar pattern in the nephelometer scattering was observed in the anti-clockwise SLR at 1000ft to the clockwise R1 at 500ft. The aircraft then performed a reciprocal turn at point #41 and headed back in an a clockwise direction to point #44 at 1500ft. A reciprocal turn was then performed and a series of saw-tooth profiles were then performed between 250ft and 5000ft to #41. The aircraft then broke off from science flying to position itself for the ‘paperclip’ manoeuvre into Canfield. Two successful passes over the airfield were performed just below the cloud base which should be useful for IRC work. The aircraft then landed and made a slow taxi with ARIES and Heimann making measurements of the runway temperature.

Summary: A successful flight with a lot of useful data for comparisons against the aerosol and the visibility forecast models. Additionally the wet-nephelometer

performed very well during the flight and showed some significant growth as a function of relative humidity.

Problems: None noted.

Jim Haywood

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.193** Date **27 April 06** Name **HAYWOOD** Page **1** of **.....**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Wind 320° 4kts, reported Cranfield.
					7/8 Sc on take off.
					Visibility ~ 10 miles.
					Cloud base ~ 2,500ft - a
					shallow layer of Cu, more cloud
					above.
~1005					Lower level cloud dissipating
					~ 1/8 Cu. Another shallow Sc
					layer at 8000ft 7/8.
10:14:18	PI	FL110	48	52.6/0.2E	1000ft/min. No Ci above,
					cloud continuing to thin.
10:23:40					Crossing coast.
10:26:45	End PI	250ft	114	52.9/1.2	End profile.
10:27:53	St RI	500ft.	122	52.8/1.4	87 → 40.
10:30					CO 150 ppbv.
					Free from cloud, but cloud
					ahead.
10:38					Sea 2/3 → no whitecaps.
10:43					Neph green = $40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$
					CO 160 ppbv.
10:48:30					Passing #41.
10:48:30					Lots of shipping on RHS
					52.33°N → general increase
					in pollution.
10:51					8/8 Alto St/STCu.
					Neph green = $80 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....193..... Date 27/04/06 Name Haywood..... age 2 of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:56					Possible ship plume → AMS + SO ₂ peaks. Sea state 2. No whitecaps. Neph reaches $\sim 1 \times 10^{-4}$ at 10:56.
11:02:00					At point #42. Very hazy visibility, 8 miles Dover cliffs visible.
11:09					Sea state 1. Glassy.
11:12					Ambient RH = 89%, neph inlet 3%
11:14:30					At point #43.
11:19					8/8 Sc
11:31:10					At point #44 Neph green $\sim 60 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ RH 87%.
11:46:40					Point #45 - ship plume at 11:43 ish
11:47:04	End R1 St P3	500ft↑	271	49.9/2.0.	
11:55:31	End P3 St P4	800ft↓			
12:00:56	Ink P4	4000ft			Turning at point #46.
12:04:50	Restart P4	4000ft↓			A few Ci clouds

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....193..... Date ..27 April 06.. NameHenry, Hood..... age3... of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:08:32	End Pt St R2	1000ft	89	50/7.8W	Profile (nep ϕ) :-
12:19:00					BBRs might be useable during the 1000ft run.
12:21:00					Cloud affecting BBRs.
12:24					Ship close to FOV.
12:32:45	End R2				End run, to look at ships with IRC. At point #44.
					400ft tanker - missed.
	Boat hunting.				Another boat, in middle. Fast - too far away.
					3 passes approx E \rightarrow W with 2 ships & a fast.
12:44:59	St R4				Plume? Fresh aerosol.
12:56					Pl #43
12:59:55					Some drizzle. Lots of plume structure.
13:01					1245 \rightarrow 1315 some interesting structure. Perhaps wet aqueous phase reactions creating sulphate?
13:11					A bit of boat drag. neg for IRC.
13:13					Point 42

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.193** Date **27th April 06** Name **Haywood** age **4** of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:15:25					More ship chasing.
13:26					Aerosol scattering dropping.
					CNC rising.
					Visibility increasing to > 25 miles
13:29:47	End R3	1000ft		51.9/1.8E	At #41.
					Boats here
13:33:57	St P5	1000ft ↑			
13:34:33	End P5 St R4	1500ft		51.7/1.6	From #41 → #42.
					Out of the top of plume until ~ 13:45, #42 → #43.
13:59:30		1500ft			#43.
					Visibility improved, ~ 20 miles;
14:05:25	End R4	1500ft			Reciprocal turn
14:07:14	St P6.1	1500ft ↓			Start sawtooth profile. #43 → #42
14:09:43	End P6.1 St P6.2	250ft ↑			
14:14:38	End P6.2 St P6.3	500ft ↓			Some cloud at FL45, penetrated.
					→ peak on neph.
14:20:04	End P6.3 St P6.4	250ft ↑			
14:25:03	End P6.4 St P6.5	500ft ↓			Some Cu (scattered), but also mid-level cloud.
14:26:30					At #42
14:31:59	End P6.5 St P6.6	250ft ↑			#42 → #41
14:32:31	End P6.6 St R5	500ft →			Good vis
14:41:43	End R5	500ft			Neph decreasing in N/E.

Mission Scientist's Log

(mission scientist 2)

Flight No **B.193** Date **27/04/06** Name **Ben Johnson** age **1** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
095006		0		Cranfield	Thin broken low level stratocumulus 7/8. Winds light and variable Temp 15°C, dewpoint 6°C
100018		0	215	Cranfield	Take off Shallow cu at 2,500ft - 3,500ft
101418	P1	FL1000	50	NE of Cranfield	SC 7-7.5 kft Decoupled multilayers in BL
102645	E P1	250ft			cloud clearing
102645	P2	250ft			
102753	E P2	800ft			
102833	R1	250ft 800ft	South	point 40	overcast, SC 8/8 but thin/hazy
103500	"	"	"	40-41	Not much aerosol, neph ~ 30 CO ~ 150, PCASP 100-200
104852	"	"	"	(Point 41)	NO ₂ and NO _x reasonably moderate levels of pollution
104800	"	"	"	"	Aerosol levels rising towards 41 at latitude 52N 20min
105500	"	"	"	41-42	CO rising to 200 neph to 100, PCASP to 1000 ←
105630	"	"	"	"	possible ship plume (spike on NO _x & lots of sulphate and SO ₂)
110000	"	"	"	"	lots of lots of nitrate in general
110200	"	"	"	Point 42	Point 42 neph, CO levels stable as values noted 1055
110500	"	"	"	"	winds 5-10 m/s N or NW quite variable for last 30 mins
110600	"	"	"	"	Fresh plume indicated by high NO _x and low O ₃
110800	"	"	"	"	No white caps on sea Sea very calm
1114.30	"	"	"	Point 43	Aerosol fairly constant neph ~ 100
113109	"	"	"	Point 44	Aerosol
114500				44-45	Winds have been 5 m/s ⁻¹ and N-NE here Neph has been ~ 80 PCASP has been ~ 800

For last 30 mins
Elevated CNC at 1135-1145 did not correlate with neph

Mission Scientist's Log

50-2
1.428 NO
NO2
~~NOx~~

Flight No **B.193** Date **27/04/06** Name **Ben Johnson** age **2** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
114704	P1	500ft	W	<u>Point 45</u>	Start profile 500ft - FLO80
114704	End P1	500ft	W		
114704	P2	500ft	W		start prof 500ft - FLO80
115831	End P3	800ft	W		neph constant to 4,500ft gradually reducing to low values of ~20 at 7000ft
115538	P4	800ft			
120056	Interrupt P4	400ft		<u>Point 46</u>	Interrupt to turn at point 46
120450	Resume P4	600ft	E		Now heading back East from 46 towards 45
120832	End P4	1000ft			clear skies at ^{point} 46 - 45
120833	start R2	1000ft			
121836	R2	1000ft	E	<u>Point 45</u>	coming under cloud 10-20 miles East of point 45
122300					A peak in CVC and SO ₂ 3000 cm ⁻³
				45-44	Spotting ships along the way.
123215	End R2	"	"	<u>Point 44</u>	Terminate run to do ship spotting for IR camera. Start
124459	R3	1000ft	E		
125300	"	"	"		CO, NOx, NO2 peak but no peak in neph 220
125700					ship plume? neph peak for 7 min neph 150
130013	"	"	"	<u>43</u>	Background values of neph ~ 80
					Another neph spike 1300 for 2 min
					Ships or individual towns? or cloud processing peaks.
1310-1320	"	"	"	"	More ship spotting around Dover Straits
1320	"	"	"	"	High nitrate levels
1320	"	"	"	"	neph ~ 100
131435				<u>Point 42</u>	

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.193** Date 27/04/06 Name Ben Johnson age 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132700	R3	1000ft	N	Thames Estuary	Coming out of the aerosol neph falling to 20, visibility very good. PCASP falling from 600 to 200 but CNC going rising very rapidly from 10.000 to 30.000 CO falling from 170 - 140 chemistry (SO ₂ , NO, NOx, NO ₂) all falling.
132947	End R3	1000ft	N	Point 41	continuing north to spot a few ships then turn onto reciprocal and returning to point 43
133357	start PE	1000ft	S		Climb to 1500ft for reciprocal run to point 43
133433	End PE	1500ft	S		
133505	133505 start R4	1500ft	S		
134500		"			Not as much aerosol at this level as when passing at 500 or 1000ft
134647		"	W	Point 42	
135941		"	W	Point 43	Thicker cloud, neph levels rising
140400		"	W	43-44	Tiny bit of drizzle here
140525	End R4	1500ft	W	"	PE
	PE	15	E	"	Turning onto reciprocal heading and preparing for sawtooths
140714	start PG1	1500ft	E	"	PE Prof 1500 - 250ft
140933	EP6.1	250ft	E	"	
140933	start P6.2	250ft	E	"	Prof 250ft - 500ft
141438	End P6.2	500ft	E	"	
141438	start P6.3	500ft	E	"	Prof 500ft - 250ft
142004	End P6.3	250ft	E	"	

141500 Big Spike is neph because we went through a cu cloud.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.193** Date **27/04/06** Name **Ben Johnson** age **7** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
141458	Start				
142004	P6.4	250ft	W	Point 43-42	Scattered CU at 4000ft 1/8 sc above 8/8
142503	End P6.4	5000ft	W	"	Neph(2)
142503	Start P6.5	5000ft	W	"	
142642				<u>Point 42</u>	
143159	End P6.5	250ft		42-41	
143259	Start P6.6	250ft		"	
143231	End P6.6	500ft		"	
143500					
143232	Start R5	500ft	N	"	
144143	End R5	500ft	N	"	Aerosol values dropped very low
144224	Start P7	500ft	NW	"	
144410			NW	<u>Near Point 41</u>	sc layer gone, Scattered CU 4/8
					Heading back toward Cranfield
144826	End P7	6,500ft	NW		cloud top 7250 7250 ft
144826	Start R6	6500ft	NW		
145331	End R6	6,500ft	W		
145340	Start P8	6,500ft	"		
145537	End P8	8,500ft	"		
145537	Start R7	8,500ft	"		approaching Cranfield
	End R7	8500ft	"		preparing for NEON 'paper clip'
					Successful paper clip maneuver at 4000 ft
141726		0	31	Cranfield	Land

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B193

Date : 27/4/06

Operator and contact info : Jamie Trembath jatr@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	Bad cals at 11:02 and 11:04UT as calibration gas flow too low
O₃	none
NO_x	None
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	None
WAS	N/A

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 193

Date: 27/04/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:32:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:14:20	85	0.09	21	5												Start Profile 1 from FL110	
10:15:04	150	0.09		2												FL100	
10:15:51	65	0.09		5												FL090	
10:16:45	25	0.09		2												FL080	
10:17:37	100	0.09		5												FL070	
10:18:24	100	0.09		2												FL060	
10:19:22	95	0.08		5												FL050	
10:20:24	85	0.08		5												FL040	
10:21:30	140	0.09		5												FL030	
10:22:47	110	0.09		5												FL020	
10:24:23	100	0.09		10												FL010	
10:26:42	310	0.08		20												End of Profile 1 @ 250'	
10:28:35																Start Run 1 @ 500'	
10:29:00	215	0.09		20													
10:31:00	200	0.09		30													
10:33:00	180	0.09		30													
10:35:00	230	0.09		20													
10:37:00	120	0.09		10													
10:39:00	190	0.08		10													
10:41:00	Noise			10													
10:43:00	330	0.09		10													
10:45:00	385	0.09		10													
10:47:00	500	0.09		10													
10:49:00	460	0.09		10													
10:51:00	850	0.09		10													
10:53:00	840	0.10		15													
10:55:00	1000	0.09		20													
10:57:00	1000	0.09		20													
10:59:00	1150	0.09		20													
11:01:00	1000	0.10		30													
11:03:00	990	0.09		20													
11:05:00	1050	0.10		30													
11:07:00	1000	0.10		20													
11:09:00	1050	0.10		20													
11:11:00	1000	0.10		20													
11:13:00	1100	0.10		20													
11:15:00	950	0.10		15													
11:17:00	900	0.10		10													
11:19:00	900	0.10		15													
11:21:00	900	0.10		10													
11:23:00	920	0.10		10													
11:25:00	760	0.10		20													
11:27:00	700	0.10		20													
11:29:00	815	0.10		15													
11:31:00	780	0.09		15													
11:33:00	795	0.10		15													

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 193

Date: 27/04/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:32:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:35:00	720	0.10	22	15													
11:39:00	830	0.09		15													
11:41:00	800	0.10		15													
11:43:00	860	0.10		10													
11:45:00	2000	0.09		10													
11:47:01																End of Run 1 & Start Profile 3	
11:48:05	560	0.09		15												FL010	
11:49:05	750	0.10		20												FL020	
11:50:14	630	0.10		20												FL030	
11:51:26	480	0.10		15												FL040	
11:52:23	330	0.09		10												FL050	
11:53:28	260	0.09		10												FL060	
11:54:31	50	0.08		5												FL070	
11:55:35	30	0.08		5												End of Profile 3 & Start Profile 4 from FL080	
11:57:16	50	0.08		5												FL070	
11:58:07	340	0.10		10												FL060	
11:59:20	480	0.10		20												FL050	
12:00:29	560	0.09		10												FL040	
12:05:31	650	0.09		10												FL030	
12:06:40	680	0.09		20												FL020	
12:08:33	620	0.09		20												End of Profile 4 & Start Run 2 @ 1000'	
12:09:00	740	0.09		20													
12:11:00	830	0.09		30													
12:13:00	925	0.09		40													
12:15:00	675	0.09		20													
12:17:00	760	0.10		10													
12:19:00	750	0.10		10													
12:21:00	750	0.10		10													
12:23:00	835	0.10		10													
12:25:00	550	0.10		10													
12:27:00	550	0.10		10													
12:29:00	800	0.09		10													
12:31:00	800	0.09		20													
12:32:47																End of Run 2	
12:45:05																Start Run 3 @ 1000'	
12:46:00	900	0.10		20													
12:48:00	770	0.10		20													
12:50:00	870	0.10		20													
12:52:00	1050	0.10		20													
12:54:00	880	0.10		20													
12:56:00	900	0.10		20													
12:58:00	990	0.10		10		2											
13:00:00	800	0.09		10													
13:02:00	580	0.09		15													
13:04:00	600	0.09		15													
13:06:00	600	0.09		15													

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 193

Date: 27/04/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:32:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:08:00	745	0.09	22	15													
13:10:00	790	0.10		15													
13:12:00	815	0.10		15													
13:14:00	800	0.10		15													
13:16:00	730	0.09		10													
13:18:00	1000	0.09		10													
13:20:00	800	0.09		10													
13:22:00	770	0.09		10													
13:24:00	600	0.09		15													
13:26:00	395	0.08		10													
13:28:00	160	0.08		10													
13:29:50																End of Run 3	
13:33:58	200	0.08														Start Profile 5	
13:34:35																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 4 @ 1500'	
13:35:00	310	0.09		10													
13:37:00	400	0.09		10													
13:39:00	560	0.09		10													
13:41:00	460	0.09		10													
13:43:00	420	0.09		10													
13:45:00	400	0.09		10													
13:47:00	440	0.09		10													
13:49:00	510	0.09		10													
13:51:00	440	0.09		10													
13:53:00	650	0.09		15													
13:55:00	680	0.09		20													
13:57:00	750	0.09		20													
13:59:00	850	0.09		20													
14:01:00	695	0.09		20													
14:03:00	800	0.09		20													
14:05:00	800	0.09		20													
14:05:28																End of Run 4	
14:07:15	800	0.09		20												Start Profile 6.1 from 1500'	
14:09:35	990	0.09		20												End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2 from 250'	
14:10:44	600	0.09		20												FL010	
14:11:43	560	0.09		20												FL020	
14:12:49	500	0.09		20												FL030	
14:13:53	250	0.10		10												FL040	
14:14:39	235	0.10		10												End of Profile 6.2 & Start P 6.3 from FL050	
14:16:20	Noise															FL030	
14:20:09	900	0.10	Reset	10												End of Profile 6.3 & Start Profile 6.4 @ 500'	
14:22:10	220	0.08	0	5												FL020	
14:23:06	120	0.08		5												FL030	
14:24:11	150	0.08		5												FL040	
14:25:02	150	0.08		5												End of Profile 6.4 & Start P6.5 @ 5000'	
14:25:57	160	0.08		5												FL040	
14:27:26	390	0.08		5												FL030	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B193**Date:**

27/04/2006

B) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B193_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B193_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	29/06/06	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B193 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B193_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown		Problems running this but Manually edited o/p file
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B193 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use, in order of preference, - if a calibration exists after the flight date, then the file that is closest in time to it, - or the most recent calibration file prior to the flight date. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	29/06/06	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL21042006.TXT Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B193_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B193_mfdX','pmsdata:B193_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	29/06/06	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto Addt=3 seconds
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B193_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:B193_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	29/06/06	
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		Yes. FSSP good agreement with Nevzorov LWC
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		Note some drop-outs of FFSSP when in cloud.
iii) Alternative at 5b) is to use ,auto=602 or auto=605 to align FFSSP with Nevzorov LWC or TWC.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B193**Date:**

27/04/2006

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B193.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B193.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B193.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B193.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B193_seadas.dat iii) exit		Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written 42927 blocks read / written
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B193 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B193_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data N j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: N l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	29/06/06	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files. Data ends c 152300 Not required Not required
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B193 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec Preparation of imagery for Core data product iii) WAVE> auto_image		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

<p>a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B193 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files</p>	<p>29/06/06</p>	<p>Image data not processed – very few blocks FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B193_2Dx-IMAGES.PS</p>
<p>ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC</p>		
<p>Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter</p>		
<p>Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files</p>		
<p>9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO a) Flight number: B193 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data</p>		
<p>e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B193_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B193_PROC2D</p>	<p>29/06/06</p>	<p>If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end. Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log. Note the particle type Data not processed</p>
<p>10) In PVWAVE</p>		
<p>i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B193_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B193_M5PROC2D' iii) exit</p>		<p>Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).</p>
<p>11) MODIFY</p>		
<p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B193_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B193_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		
<p>12) CHECKS:</p>		
<p>i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?</p>		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B193**Date:**

27/04/2006

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures B193_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: B193 b) File name: PMSDATA:B193_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:B193_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:B193_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:B193_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d) g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	1 1.0 095000 152400	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate But note occasional noise Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
3) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B193_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:B193_m5procpcasp' iii) exit		Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
4) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B193_m5procpcasp b) Datset: mfddata:B193_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	MFDB 29/06/06	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B193**Date:**

27/04/2006

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC		
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults		Defaults in [square brackets]
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:B193_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B193.nc]		As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated
2) Ftp transfer to BADC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B193.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B193.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B193_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary	29/06/06	Complete

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:B193*.* outdir:B193_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.	29/06/06	Note destination directory "outdir" In CLOUD_PHYS:[BROWN.PMSZIP]

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B193**Date:**

27/04/2006

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC B193_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B193_FFSSP_HVMS.txt B193_FFSSP.raw B193_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B193_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS B193.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (B193.zip) - rename B193.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B193_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B193_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B193_rawseadas.zip	29/06/06	Binary data transfer complete

ARIES flight log

Flight: B193

Location: English Channel

page 1 of

Date: 27/04/06

Operator(s): Cross Kern

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2

B: 2

Notes: No probs on ground.

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Sht	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
10217										Scan rate just starting to step down to 60 scans/win This was during people down from FL110 →
10222										Scan rate mainly 60
102442	Rerun	PC								reboot made it worse, stuck on 60 scans/win
103747	R1									Windows tried to reformatting software & reboots PC has got the scans working again - don't know how?
103913	R1 500'	B193C	CSD	71.1	19.3	14.3	-190.6	27.5	CH1	cal.
104041	R1 500'	B193D	Open	70.7	19.7	14.5	-189.9	27.0	Z1 x 2	Clear above.
104314		B193E	CSD	71.0	21.5	16.0	-190.6	24.8	N1 x 2	Seems to go slow.
104732	R1	B193F	CSD	71.0	21.4	16.4	-190.6	25.3	CH1	
104950	R1	B193G	CSD							IR - Foot - mac 16cm ⁻¹
										Reversed back to 1cm ⁻¹ , scan rate failed. - Rebooted, now OK.
1056:00	Restored	flight recording								
105735	R1 500'	B193H	CSD	70.9	22.6	16.7	-190.6	25.9	N1 x 2	Cloud above.
105939	R1 500'	B193I	CSD	70.9	22.7	16.9			CH1	
110220	R1 way back	B193J	CSD		5					IR - Foot 16cm ⁻¹ test for returning to 1cm ⁻¹ . ok!
	Paper Clip	B193K	CSD							IR - Foot 16cm ⁻¹ 1st part of paper clip
	" "	B193L	CSD							IR - Foot 16cm ⁻¹ 2nd part of paper clip
114440	" "	B193M	CSD	70.0	22.1	16.9	-189.9	23.9	CH1	Cal. - full scan rate caps!

1519?? TAXI B193O CSD 70.7 22.6 16.7 -189.9 24.6 CH1 NI x 1

152023 TAXI B193G CSD 70.7 22.6 16.7 -189.9 24.6 CH1

Runway view
CAT on gnd.

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	27/4/06	Flight	B193	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Bowles		Campaign	VISURB			
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield			

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						X
FERA on					at time	08:24
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	16.8°C	Ch	16.7°C	Ch18	16.3°C
Temperature controller set points		54.0°C	17	58.0°C	-20	40.0°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	08:27
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289.3	Cold	287.3		
Target heating						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	08:28
Scan indication	Monitor)	Visual	X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	Not flown, IR camera in use					
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						X
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud			Precip		
	Surface			Pressure		
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	08:30	
Brightness temps 'sensible'	Yes				
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.5	Cold	290.47
	Deimos:	Hot	NA	Cold	NA
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)
	nothing	33.37	38.47	41.07	42.94

Power changeover

Headset on before start	
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)	
Exit Deimos Software (x)	
POWER CHANGEOVER	
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton
Restart Deimos Software	
System running again	at time

IR Camera Log B193 27/04/06 class Kent.

Pre-flight cal
cold

08:27:38 20°C.
08:28:38 20°C.
08:29:38 20°C

Hot.

08:50:38 62
08:51:38 → 62.
08:52:38 63
08:53:38 64
08:54:38 65
08:55:38 65
08:56:38 66.

Time	Height	Comments
12:40 → 15	1000'	Algal bloom?
12:26:24	1000'	Across a ships wake, maybe a ship?
12:35 ⁹⁰ ish -	1000'	various ships + fort - got some birds
12:38'ish -	1000'	same ships + fort but from other direction
12:44'ish -	1000'	same ships + fort again.
13:15 → 17'ish	1000'	various ferries.
13:29:34		
13:32:30 - 13:33:44	1000'	various ships @ anchor.
13:39'ish	1500'	various kinkers
Pope clip manoeuvre.		
15:09:33	15:10:05	4500'
		1st Part of Paperclip
15:12:32	15:12:46	4500'
		2nd Part of Paperclip

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.193**.....

 Date 27/4/06.....

 Operator's name: Wilson/OSBORNE.....

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GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
0852								zero calcs OK. RH's OK. dry RH suspect? at 25% Humidity ratios in order of 1.15. Good. ↳ (40% → 65%)
101230						↑ 35c		Ramp to 35c
102500						→	40c	
102500			14.0	32.4	84.6%	→	42c	Ramping up for profile.
103027	Scoft		13.6	48.7	92.8	↘	5c	Ramp down during run @ 500ft
104000	Scoft1		13.3	39.9	50.8	↗	41c	W:D ratio is 1 so ramping up to 41c
104740	P1	"	13.2	44.4	87.6	→	40c	Creep up.
105029	Scoft		13.3	44.0	91	↘	5c	Ratios W:D of 1.5. Now ramping down.
110039	"		13.3	46	51	↗	41c	
111248	"		13.4	43.2	88.3	↘	5c	Ramping down after W:D growth factors at 1.65 (ish).
111950	"		13.4	38.7	54.6	↗	42c	and up!
112450	"		13.4	37.6	84.6	→	43c	Creep up.
112637	"		13.3	40.9	87.2	→	44c	Creep up.
112940	"		13.5	41.2	90.6	↘	5c	RAMPING DOWN RH1 = 32.2% RH3 = 24.8%
114022	"		13.3	36.7	48.2	↗	42c	going up RH1 28.6% RH5: 46.4%
114940			15.0		84.6			flow increased as RH5 near 100%

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.193**.....

 Date 27/4/06.....

 Operator's name: Wilson / Osborne.....

 Page 2 of 3.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
120620		4000ft	14	28.5	87.4	↗	45°C	ramp to max.
120953		/	12.8	36.3	93.6	↘	5°C	ramp to min. W:D ratio 1.8.
122040		/	12.8	32.1	50.2	↗	45°C	to max. U:D total 1.05.
122535		/	12.6	32.1	83.7	↘	20°C	Marked deliquescent line at 70%. Cycling between (deliquescent) 65 & 75% a few times.
12		500ft	12.8					
12		500ft	12.8	38.3	59.7	↗	40°C	ramping up thro' deli line.
123410			12.7	38.3	80.4	↘	20°C	& down thro' deli line.
123844		500ft	12.8	37.6	57.5	↗	40°C	
124130		---		38	77.5			no deli line visible in this last ramp.
124317		---	12.7	38	81	↘	20°C	and down thro' humidity.
124805		---	---	39.3	57.1	↘	5°C	ramping to min.
125050		---	12.7	36.3	49.4	↗	45°C	to max.
130210		---	13.1	39	88.3	↘	5°C	to min. W:D ratio 1.6.
131105		---	12.9	41.2	51.9	↗	42.5°C	going up.
131340								just flow thro' ship exhaust plumes. W:D of 1.8 @ 65% RH
1320								visible on wet neph.
132035		---	13.9	39.6	87	↘	5°C	to min
132801		---	13.8	29.8	50.2	↗	42.5°C	up again. W:D at 1.1
133415		---	13.7	27.5	84.8	↗	44°C	a bit more.
133630		1000ft.	13.7	31.5	87.4	↘	5°C	and down.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 193 Date: 27th April 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	N
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	N	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	Y		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	Y
SWS	N	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B193

Date: 27 April 2006

Instruments

1. Problems with lat long on HORACE updating – needed to reset DLU then appeared OK – no problems on mission scientist screen?
2. Cannot plot YX plots on HORACE
3. CO cal gas pressure not set to 3 bar

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom Calls

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B193:

Log	Reason
IR Camera Processing log	IR Camera Processing log not currently available
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Forward Facing Cameras
1 x Downward Facing Cameras
1 x Down/Upward Facing Cameras
2 x Upward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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